

TEACHING STUDENTS IN AN INNOVATIVE WAY

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Abstract. *The role of technology to make a better education system, Short abstracts about how to create an innovative environment.*

In recent decades, each thing in our society has changed and still in its way, still developing in a second. But it is education that has been a subject for many debates for many years, and most of them are claiming to develop it. Let's talk about innovation in education, discuss few examples, and find out why it is important. As teachers and students our goal is solely develop our education system and in this way, I think each of us should give our contribution and it is innovation which can help us in this way.

Innovation is one of those words we like to throw around whenever possible. To innovate means to make changes or do something in a new way. To innovate does not require you to invent something. Baked into innovation is creativity and adaptability. Innovation in education is not a specific term with fixed definitions. The spirit of innovation education is an openness to looking with fresh eyes at problems and to address them in different, new ways.

Innovation in education comes from identifying problems, watching and learning from others, to develop new methods to address these problems, and iterating on them when these experiments do not necessarily give the results you need.

It is nearly impossible to predict or keep pace with the rate of change on today's workplace. Accepting that, we can then agree that perhaps more important than the knowledge we have is the ability to adapt and evolve. Innovation education helps prepare students for a dynamic workplace by providing them, opportunities to develop skills such as creativity, adaptability and resilience.

As our goal is solely develop our country by improving educational facilities and creating educational opportunities we also have to adapt new changes and should start to live with them. It is true innovation, especially technology is one of the barriers to improve our education because it is phones, computers and social media which is disturbing students to develop their skills and even doing their typically homework given by teachers but I think it can help us to create a new, perfect education as we dreamed, even more than we thought. To achieve this we have to learn how to work with technology, how to apply it in our education system.

As an example to education innovation, we can count Kaltura virtual classrooms. Kaltura virtual classrooms has been designed and built for education and training. Teachers can conduct interactive, face-to-face classes that actively engage remote students. Teachers are not simply connecting face-to-face to lecture passive students. The platform provides tools that allow teachers to introduce innovation in education.

Here in the picture an example of Kaltura virtual classes is given.

I honestly think that, in the past decades our education also witnessed dramatic increase in each field. At the same time, new innovative technologies of scientific and technical education are being introduced more and more in the world. In Uzbekistan, the prerequisites and conditions are being created for the transition to such teaching technologies, which is reflected in the Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. Of great importance in this direction is the creation of a system of presidential schools, where gifted children who graduated from the fourth grade according to test results are selected.

Presidential schools are already operating in Tashkent, Namangan, Nukus and Khiva, schools are opening in Bukhara, Jizzak, Samarkand and Fergana this year, and in 2021 they will be opened in Andijan, Navoi, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya and Tashkent regions. Specialized educational institutions with in-depth study of ICT, exact sciences, as well as aerospace and astronomy are being created. Thus, by the decrees of the President, a school named after alKhorezmi and a boarding school named after Mirzo Ulugbek were established in Tashkent at the Astronomical Institute of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The aim of the school is preparation of future leaders, students of the nation, who will be able to win international Olympiads, competitions and get access to the best universities in the world, to educate leaders who can be globally competitive. Additionally this can be one of these developments in our education system, and I think these improvement will give their fruits in the near future.

To give a better reply to these kinds of reforms in our education system, we, youth also should try hard as students of higher education, and use new opportunities which are being created by our president, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev.

Here as our president Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev said: *“Improving the quality of education is the only right way to the development of the New Uzbekistan.”*

In this way, innovation helps us to build the education system as we craved, as we expected. If we know how to use technology in a right way it will be easier to get it.

Innovation in education can be:

- Recognizing that students are better served by a flipped classroom where they watch lectures at home and complete assignments in the classroom.
- Introducing more technology in the classroom to create a blended classroom where students experience technology as they would in the real world
- Providing greater ways to facilitate clearer and better communication between school districts’ parents with powerful video tools.

Very often we find ourselves in a time and place where the status quo is the goal. We may be coasting with enough success in the classroom that there isn’t much appetite to shake things up. For better or worse, that isn’t the current landscape and not one we can expect to return to anytime soon. In conclusion, in order to reach that level we craved in our education we should use the ways which are innovative, can address problems because we have already used the traditional ways of teaching but now it is time to create, it is time to innovate something useful.

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